

Uneven Governance, Unequal Impacts: Reflections on the Social and Political Dimensions of the Covid-19 Pandemic

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ENDURE - DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.16899785

This report brings together findings and reflections from a multi-sited research and public engagement process that examined the social, political, economic and cultural dimensions of COVID-19 pandemic governance in Croatia and beyond. Drawing from feminist, critical race, anthropological, political science and public sociology frameworks, it interrogates how crisis governance both reinforced and revealed inequalities—particularly across lines of race, class, gender, age, and citizenship. While centering the Croatian case, the analysis is embedded in broader European and global contexts, foregrounding minoritized experiences, community resilience, and civic contestation. Through original research, workshops, and local and transnational collaborations, the report seeks to re-politicize the pandemic as a moment of rupture and possibility, and to contribute to a deeper understanding of crisis governance, its afterlives, and the collective futures it forecloses—or makes imaginable.

Covid-19 Pandemic Governance Analysis

The Covid-19 pandemic revealed the deep entanglement of health governance with political power, institutional trust, and crisis management capacities across Europe. Governments adopted emergency measures at an unprecedented scale, mobilizing resources through public health orders, curfews, digital surveillance, and new welfare schemes. Yet, this was not a monolithic response; governance was marked by fragmentation, improvisation, and path dependency—deeply shaped by national political cultures, institutional legacies, and hegemonic ideologies.

The introduction to the *Critical Sociology* special issue *Crisis Governance, (De)Mobilisation, and New Inequalities: Framing the Legacy of COVID-19* (Bužinkić, Foley & Kerr, 2024) argues that the pandemic represents one of the most significant transformations of state-society relations in recent history—second only to wartime or revolutionary moments. Pandemic governance in Europe involved extraordinary state interventions: emergency powers, lockdowns, border controls, and economic halts. Yet these actions unfolded not through a rupture with liberal democratic norms but via their own path-dependent logics, raising urgent questions for political theory, particularly within Marxist and Foucauldian traditions, and transnational critical and feminist itineraries.

While early analyses framed these interventions as either departures from or openings beyond neoliberalism, the reality was more ambiguous. States temporarily de-mobilized civil society and small capital while centralizing power, often with broad public support. This peculiar

consent—combined with militarized metaphors and heightened surveillance—challenges conventional interpretations of state coercion and control. Rather than producing collectivization or systemic transformation, governance responses often reproduced and deepened existing inequalities, particularly along lines of race, class, age, gender, and citizenship.

The special issue, conceptualized at a partners meeting and a workshop at the University of Glasgow in October 2023, aims to counter the growing “lockdown amnesia” in political discourse and academic scholarship. Drawing from the ENDURE Project, the editors call for renewed attention to the long-term socio-political effects of crisis governance. Through comparative case studies across five European states, the collection examines how pandemic measures intersected with existing structures of inequality, exclusion, and hegemonic power, while also exploring the forms of resistance and survival mobilized by minoritized and precarious populations. It seeks to re-politicize the pandemic by situating it within longer histories of state transformation and social contestation.

The *Critical Sociology* special issue *Crisis Governance, (De)Mobilisation, and New Inequalities* thus situates the Covid-19 pandemic as a historic rupture in the governance of liberal-democratic states. Rather than marking a clear departure from neoliberalism, the pandemic revealed its mutations: emergency powers were deployed through existing institutional pathways, often bypassing democratic oversight while invoking the language of protection and collective sacrifice. This paradox—of democratic states acting undemocratically with widespread public support—frames a key puzzle for contemporary critical theory.

Contributing to this debate, Emina Bužinkić and Senada Šelo Šabić’s article *COVID-19 Emergency Governance in Croatia: The Case of Perpetual Exception and Securitized Disenfranchisement* provides an incisive analysis of how these dynamics manifested in Croatia (Bužinkić & Šelo Šabić, 2024). The authors argue that Croatian pandemic governance did not formally declare a state of emergency but instead operated through a “state of exception” that was functionally indistinguishable. This choice—avoiding constitutional frameworks while enacting sweeping restrictions—allowed the state to consolidate power in a manner that revived and reinforced ethno-nationalist and securitizing logics rooted in post-war crisis governance.

Through two case studies, the article traces how these modes of governance disproportionately impacted minoritized populations, especially migrants and racially marked communities. Emergency measures, justified as public health responses, were selectively applied in ways that reproduced structural inequalities and denied access to protection and mobility. The Croatian case illustrates how crisis governance can simultaneously appear benign and technocratic, yet function as a mechanism of exclusion, surveillance, and racialized control, particularly in post-socialist states with entrenched nationalist paradigms. The crisis governance framework relied on technocratic and securitized language, portraying the virus as an external threat and positioning state actors as protectors of the “public good.” In doing

so, it obscured the social and racialized dimensions of vulnerability, particularly among those already marginalized by structural inequalities.

Racialized groups—including migrant workers, Roma communities, and asylum seekers—faced intensified scrutiny and exclusion. In countries like Croatia, pandemic measures disproportionately targeted asylum seekers in reception centers, where fencing, surveillance, and isolation reinforced racialized borders within the state. Access to healthcare and information was often unequal, compounded by language barriers, mistrust in institutions, and legal precarity.

This research was presented at two key international conferences. At the Central and East European International Studies Association (CEEISA) conference in Rijeka in 2024, it was shared under the title *The Politics of (De)Mobilization and Multiple Pandemics*. At the International Sociological Association (ISA) Forum in Rabat, Morocco in 2025, it was presented as *Storying Social Distancing*, connecting it to research developed during Bužinkić's doctoral study. These engagements provided an opportunity to situate the Croatian case within broader comparative discussions on the political legacies of the pandemic and the reshaping of democratic governance across diverse geopolitical contexts.

Moreover, this research helped lay the groundwork for a forthcoming edited volume titled *The Organization of Irresponsibility?: Reassessing COVID-19 in Europe*, edited by Kerr, Bužinkić, and Foley, and expected to be published in November 2025 by Brill.

Social Differentiation of Impact: Gender, Class, Age

Female Teachers in Minoritized Education

Pandemic governance did not affect all equally. Rather, it exposed and deepened pre-existing inequalities along lines of gender, age, race, class and citizenship. Women—especially those in frontline, care, and educational roles—bore a disproportionate burden, balancing paid labor with unpaid domestic work, often in precarious and undervalued sectors. Reports across Europe documented spikes in burnout, job loss, and domestic violence, particularly affecting single mothers, migrant care workers, and racialized women. Governance throughout the pandemic oscillated between the expansion of state control—over health, mobility, and data—and the intensification of neoliberal logics that privatized care, shifting responsibilities onto individuals and families. This dual movement underscored the fragility and inequality of the social contract in times of crisis.

Within this broader context, our research on female teachers in minoritized education in Croatia provides a grounded account of how gendered labor, nationhood, and neoliberalism converged under pandemic conditions. Titled *Precarity of Female Teachers in Minoritized Education in Croatia: Nationhood, Capitalism, and Care in COVID-19 (Post)Pandemic Worlds*, the study, co-authored by Emina Bužinkić and Nina Čolović, examines the lived realities of educators working in Serb minority schools and refugee-inclusive classrooms—often located

in under-resourced, rural areas shaped by ethno-nationalist hierarchies and infrastructural neglect.

Presented at the 7th International Conference *Social Boundaries of Work* in Wrocław (2025) under the title *Female Teachers in Minoritized Education in Croatia: Precarity, Nationhood, and the Capitalist Neoliberal Grammar*, and at the *Comparative and International Education Society (CIES)* conference (2025) under the title *Challenging the Crisis: Female Teachers, Capitalism, and Nationhood in Croatia's Minoritized Education Amidst COVID-19*, this research challenges the tendency to frame education as a technocratic or politically neutral field. Drawing on critical education research, we analyze schools as ideological state apparatuses, where racialized and gendered inequalities were intensified during the pandemic.

Teachers became digital laborers, informal healthcare mediators, caregivers, and biopolitical managers, enforcing quarantines and vaccination protocols while managing the emotional, material, and educational fallout for their students. For those in minoritized settings, this work was compounded by systemic neglect—language inequalities, lack of resources for refugee students, and decades of institutional marginalization. Teachers navigated this terrain largely unsupported, performing unpaid, unrecognized labor in order to hold their classrooms—and communities—together.

Narratives collected during fieldwork reveal a complex terrain of compliance, resistance, and exhaustion. Teachers were celebrated as essential, yet rendered disposable. Many internalized their role in reproducing national and capitalist logics, but some resisted—by teaching about inequality, mentoring asylum-seeking children, or creating cooperative spaces where students could exchange skills and stories.

Pandemic conditions also dissolved boundaries between work and home. Teachers reported teaching through illness, mourning loved ones without institutional support, and being surveilled via remote learning platforms that intruded into their private spaces. They juggled their own children's education while keeping classrooms afloat. We conceptualize this condition as “crisis precarity”—an entanglement of affective labor, bodily strain, caregiving demands, and infrastructural collapse.

Still, amidst the crisis, teachers forged forms of collective care. They translated public health materials, pooled resources, and supported marginalized students. Their experiences illustrate not only the failures of pandemic governance, but also the depth of feminist and community-based strategies of survival and solidarity.

This study was initially discussed and peer reviewed in an internal workshop in Istanbul in March 2024. The study will appear as a chapter in the forthcoming edited volume *Global Essential Workers*, edited by Karolak, Mrozowicki, and Varga, scheduled for publication by the end of 2025. The volume brings together critical international perspectives on labor, inequality, and the essential work that sustains communities during systemic disruption.

Homelessness in the Pandemic: Governance by Abandonment

The COVID-19 pandemic starkly illuminated the structural failures of Croatia's social welfare system, particularly in its treatment of unhoused individuals. These failures, however, did not begin with the pandemic. They are rooted in decades of neoliberal restructuring, during which universal welfare protections were eroded and responsibilities for care were offloaded onto under-resourced civil society organizations and fragmented local administrations. The crisis merely amplified the effects of this long-standing institutional abandonment.

As the Croatian government mobilized rapidly to enforce public health mandates—curfews, border closures, and emergency declarations—it simultaneously withdrew from safeguarding the basic rights of homeless populations. This withdrawal revealed a telling contradiction: while the state retains coercive and regulatory power, it has abdicated its obligations as a provider of care. Appeals from the Croatian Homeless Network (2020), especially following the March 2020 earthquake that devastated parts of Zagreb, laid bare this gap. Civil society actors stepped in to care for high-risk individuals—elderly, chronically ill, migrants—often without adequate state support, even as they themselves faced infrastructural collapse and pandemic strain.

Warnings from the Office of the Public Ombudsman further underscored the multidimensional vulnerability of people experiencing homelessness: absence of health insurance, limited access to reliable information, unsanitary conditions, and systemic exclusion from public health services. Public calls for solidarity and collective responsibility rang hollow for those left with no means to comply.

This neglect was especially visible during the vaccine rollout. Bureaucratic barriers—such as the requirement of a registered address or a designated primary care physician—effectively excluded many homeless individuals from accessing vaccines. Despite general guidance available on the government's COVID-19 portal, there were no specific strategies or targeted outreach efforts to ensure protection for unhoused populations. Even where social welfare protocols evolved between 2020 and 2022, homeless people were subsumed into vague categories of “vulnerable groups,” erasing the specific intersecting challenges they face—housing insecurity, mental health issues, chronic illness, and legal precarity.

Estimates suggest that nearly 10,000 people in Croatia live in insecure or inadequate housing, yet fewer than 600 are formally recognized within state welfare systems (FRA, 2020). This undercount reflects a broader trend in urban governance—particularly in Zagreb—where housing has been increasingly commodified, and public housing stock diminished, pushing more people into marginality.

The Croatian state's pandemic response to homelessness exemplifies a pattern of governance by abandonment: swift and decisive action to secure borders and control populations, yet consistent inaction when it comes to ensuring care for society's most vulnerable. The state's retreat from social protection responsibilities is not an oversight, but a reflection of how neoliberal governance operationalizes neglect. By treating homelessness as a logistical or disciplinary issue—rather than a matter of rights and justice—pandemic governance entrenched exclusion, rather than alleviating it.

This research underscores the urgent need to reimagine the social contract. What is required is not only emergency aid, but long-term commitments to housing justice, universal health access, and the right to care. Only then can we confront the deeper inequalities that the pandemic has made impossible to ignore.

This research is currently being developed into a manuscript and will be submitted for publication before the end of 2025.

Quarantine as Both Isolation and Escape for Youth

For young people, the COVID-19 pandemic was not only a disruption to education, but an existential breach in the rhythms and expectations of everyday life. The closure of schools, restrictions on movement, and the sudden shift to digital learning created deep disorientation, intensifying feelings of anxiety and social isolation—particularly among students already marginalized by economic precarity or digital exclusion. And yet, amid these disruptions, the pandemic also opened unexpected spaces of pause, reflection, and resistance.

In a series of workshops facilitated by Emina Bužinkić between November 2024 and April 2025—at the University of Ljubljana's Department for Ethnology and Cultural Anthropology, the Pedagogical Faculty at the University of Bihać, and the University of Rijeka's Faculty of Teacher Education—students shared intimate narratives of how they lived through quarantine. Many spoke of loss: of grandparents and parents to COVID-19, of missed rites of passage, and of the everyday companionship of peers. But alongside this grief, they described the quarantine as paradoxically liberating. For some, it was the first real pause in years—a break from the relentless churn of schoolwork, part-time jobs, and familial expectations. The enforced stillness offered space to rest, to think, to be. As several students put it, it was a chance to finally “breathe.”

Crucially, these moments of reprieve were not framed as simply personal or incidental. Many participants interpreted their experience as a structural critique of the world they inhabit. They expressed frustration that the pandemic had to happen in order for them to reclaim time—time that capitalist routines had long denied them. They spoke of cycles of overwork, overachievement, and emotional depletion, and of a desire for a world in which rest, connection, and slowness are not luxuries but rights. Several students even confessed to

wishing, quietly and guiltily, for the return of quarantine—not because of the virus, but because it offered a glimpse of a less extractive way of being.

These reflections illuminate the layered nature of youth experience during the pandemic: grief intertwined with relief, isolation with introspection, rupture with recalibration. Rather than being understood solely as a generation “set back” by the crisis, young people in these conversations emerged as critical thinkers—articulating new imaginaries for life beyond neoliberal urgency. Their testimonies reveal an emergent consciousness of time, care, and resistance, grounded in both the trauma and the clarity that the crisis unearthed.

These stratified youth experiences are not accidental. They reflect the racialized, gendered, and classed architecture of pandemic governance. Crises that claim to affect all equally often reproduce and deepen existing inequalities. By centering the perspectives of those multiply burdened—young people, racialized communities, undocumented migrants, and women in frontline roles—we gain insight into how pandemic governance did not simply manage a virus but reshaped the contours of a deeply unequal social contract.

Community Resilience

Community resilience, as one of the central pieces of the ENDURE project, culminated in the *Community Resilience Lab*, held in Zagreb from April 22 to 26, 2025. Marked as the closing chapter of the ENDURE project, it brought together over 150 researchers, artists, educators, and community members to reflect on how communities resist and reimagine in times of crisis. Moving beyond institutional narratives of “recovery,” the Lab foregrounded community knowledge, embodied memory, and collective care as modes of resilience forged in conditions of abandonment.

Through three interwoven events—a research forum, a conference, and a legislative theatre gathering—the Lab traced the social ruptures exposed by the pandemic and the solidarities that emerged in response. The *Research Forum on Community Resilience and Social Inequalities* focused on the fragmentation of education, healthcare, and social protections, and the mutual aid practices that quietly filled their absence. Participants emphasized that resilience is not individual adaptability, but a practice of political care rooted in migrant justice, anti-racism, and grassroots infrastructure.

The *Conference on Integration as a Contested Process* challenged technocratic understandings of integration, centering migrant voices and community organizing. Instead of treating integration as an institutional benchmark, it was reframed as a space of struggle—where refusal, reinvention, and coalition-building intersect. Mohammed Badran’s keynote underscored the power of migrant-led knowledge, care work, and grassroots solidarity. The final day, *Thinking & Being With Community*, offered a participatory performance through legislative theatre, opening a space for collective reflection on migration, legal precarity, and the bureaucratization of life. Stories like refugee Chia’s laid bare the structural violence

embedded in migration and labor regimes, while shared meals affirmed hospitality as both sustenance and solidarity.

This work continued in June 2025 with *Community Organising for All*, a follow-up event that deepened these themes through participatory cultural work and migrant-led organizing. Across both gatherings, community resilience was not framed as institutional durability but as a collective practice of refusal, repair, and radical imagination. Together, these two events traced pathways of community resilience rooted not in institutional stability but in shared struggle, radical care, and the everyday labor of imagining otherwise.

Further Research: Resistance, Resilience, and the Reconfiguration of Civic Life

The COVID-19 pandemic has not only strained public health infrastructures and economic systems—it has also exposed the limitations of governance and the transformative potential of civic action. These dynamics are at the heart of the research paper *Civic Mobilization and the Limits of Governance: Social Responses to COVID-19 in Croatia*, co-authored by Senada Šelo Šabić and Emina Bužinkić and presented at the ENDURE Final Workshop *Resilience/Resistance in an Age of Global Uncertainties* in March 2025 held in Brazil at the University of Campiñas.

The paper explores how crisis governance catalyzed both visible and invisible forms of civic response. On one end, anti-vaccination protests exemplified public dissent and revealed the fragility of state authority amid growing institutional mistrust. On the other, informal solidarity networks emerged in spaces where the state was absent—mutual aid efforts, neighborhood support systems, and everyday practices of care that operated outside formal politics and NGOs. These civic actions were not simply reactive; they signal a reconfiguration of political participation grounded in survival, autonomy, and refusal of extractive governance.

Rooted in longstanding critiques of neoliberalism and institutional legitimacy, these practices challenge dominant frameworks of citizenship and civic engagement. They suggest that resilience, when paired with resistance, becomes a mode of claiming space, shaping social relations, and building alternatives in the cracks of systemic failure.

Building on this work, the Croatian research team has joined the University of Wisconsin-led TAP consortium in conducting a nationwide survey on organizations, COVID-19, politics, and civic participation. This research captures the racial, gendered, ethnic, and classed contours of Croatian society, while tracing how power asymmetries shape access to political voice and public visibility. It also maps the populations most impacted by the pandemic and those for whom public health measures triggered refusal, protest, or quiet resistance. The research aims and structure was agreed on during the partners meeting in Zagreb in June 2023.

Still in the process of analysis, this data promises to inform future scholarship on civic life, inequality, and democratic possibility in post-pandemic contexts. A forthcoming comparative study with Polish researchers will deepen this inquiry, drawing on social participation clusters

developed by the Polish team to examine cross-national patterns of engagement and refusal. This widening was made possible during the workshop in Brazil.

Together, these research strands gesture toward the urgent need to examine the ambivalent space where resilience and resistance converge. Future research must grapple with how civic actors contest and reimagine democracy—not only through overt mobilization but through acts of care, refusal, and everyday survival in conditions of precarity. In doing so, we begin to trace the contours of an emergent civic horizon shaped not by institutional promises, but by collective insistence on justice and life otherwise.

Key Takeaways

- **Pandemic governance in Croatia operated through a “state of exception”** that bypassed formal constitutional frameworks while enacting securitized and racialized control, particularly targeting migrants and other marginalized groups.
- **Minoritized female teachers, homeless communities, and refugee youth bore the brunt of systemic neglect**, revealing how gendered, racialized, and classed forms of abandonment were masked by technocratic crisis responses.
- **Young people articulated a structural critique of time and exhaustion**, finding in the stillness of quarantine a fleeting glimpse of life outside capitalist urgency—underscoring the pandemic as a generational break in temporality, not just education.
- **Community resilience emerged not from institutions but from grassroots care, refusal, and collective survival**, with teacher-student communities, migrant-led organizing, and mutual aid practices offering pathways of solidarity and political imagination.
- **Civic life during the pandemic was reconfigured through both visible protest and quiet refusal**, as people built alternative infrastructures in the void left by failing governance—revealing resistance not as opposition alone, but as life-making practice. These protests also revealed a broader discontent: parts of the population rose against national governments and neoliberal globalization that continue to strip people of democracy and the possibility of living freely—free from the theft of time, health and rights.

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Forthcoming:

Kerr, E., Bužinkić, E. and Foley, J. (2025) *The Organization of Irresponsibility?: Reassessing COVID-19 in Europe*. Leiden: Brill

Bužinkić, E. & Čolović, N. (2025). Precarity of Female Teachers in Minoritized Education in Croatia: Nationhood, Capitalism, and Care in COVID-19 (Post)Pandemic Worlds. In *Karolak, M., Mrozowicki, A. & Varga, M. (eds) Global Essential Workers*.

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